

Synthesis and Characterisation of some New Diorganoselenium/tellurium Compounds and a Comparative Study of their Antimicrobial Activity

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Antibacterial and antifungal activities of organoselenium compounds are well known¹. The antimicrobial activity of organoselenium compounds is many times more than the sulphur and oxygen analogs² having isosteric elements. However, literature regarding the tellurium analog is very scanty.

In continuation of our work, the synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial activity of some newer organoselenium and organotellurium compounds of the type (ArCO)₂MCl₂ are reported here.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds showed a characteristic ir peak at 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Compounds **1e** and **1f** exhibited $\nu(\text{C}-\text{NO}_2)$ band at 1520 and 1320 cm⁻¹. In the far-ir region the compounds exhibited $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Se})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Te})$ at 460–500 and 520–450 cm⁻¹ respectively. ¹H nmr spectra of compound **1b** showed a multiplet at τ 2.2–2.5 (aromatic protons) and 2.9–3.1 and 2.8 (aliphatic proton). **1d** showed two doublets at τ 2.6–2.7 and 2.9–3.0 and a multiplet at τ 3.6–3.7 (protons of furan ring). In the mass spectrum of compound **1a** no molecular ion peak was observed (m/z 411). The base peak for ion [SeCl₂]⁺ was observed at m/z 149. Other fragments are observed at m/z 242–244 [RSeCl]⁺, 313 [R-CO]⁺ and at 103 [R⁺]. Fragmentation pattern of tellurium analog was observed almost similar.

Experimental

The solvents were dried and freshly distilled before use. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 L spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a JEOL RJMS-D 300, JEC 980 B instrument. Se and Te were estimated according to the known reported method³.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd no	Ar	M	Mol formula	m p °C	%Se/Te Found/ (Cacl d)
1a	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	Se	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ SeCl ₂	150	18.82 (18.97)
1b	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	Te	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ TeCl ₂	120	27.68 (27.76)
1c	C ₄ H ₃ O-CH=CH ^a -	Se	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ SeCl ₂	>260	19.85 (19.94)
1d	C ₄ H ₃ O ^a -	Te	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₄ TeCl ₂	140	32.76 (32.90)
1e	(<i>m</i>)NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	Se	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₆ N ₂ SeCl ₂	145	17.26 (17.37)
1f	(<i>m</i>)NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	Te	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₆ N ₂ TeCl ₂	160	25.42 (25.59)

^aC₄H₃O- is 2-furyl

Diaroyltellurium/selenium dichlorides (1a-f) : The acid chlorides were prepared by reported method⁴. Finely powdered acid was refluxed with thionyl chloride (2 mols per mol of acid) on a water-bath for 4–5 h using CaCl₂ guard-tube. An oily, clear solution of acid chloride was ob-

tained. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed by azeotropic distillation with benzene under reduced pressure.

A general method used to synthesise compounds **1a-f** was as follows. A mixture of the corresponding acid chloride (0.01 mol) and metal powder (selenium/tellurium; 200 mesh), (0.005 g-atom) in dry benzene was refluxed on a water-bath in anhydrous conditions using a CaCl₂ guard-tube for several hours. The reaction was followed by tlc. The reaction mixture was then repeatedly extracted with hot benzene and the crude product obtained after the removal of the solvent was crystallised from appropriate solvents, e.g. benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for **1a, b** and **f**, chloroform for **1d** and benzene for **1c** and **e**.

Biological activity : All the compounds were tested for their antimicrobial activity by the reported method⁵. Maximum concentration tested was 100 µg ml⁻¹ in DMSO. The compounds were tested against bacteria *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (penicillin resistance 2500 units) and fungi *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporotrichum schenckii*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

The screening results of the compound showed that organoselenium compounds possess higher antimicrobial activity than the tellurium analogs. Minimum inhibitory concentration of selenium compounds against various bacteria and fungi were found in the range of 6.25–50 µg ml⁻¹ and

0.78–50 µg ml⁻¹ respectively. Compound **1c** (selenium analog) was found to be most active against three testing bacteria (*S.f*, *P.a* and *S.a*, 6.25, 6.25 and 25 µg ml⁻¹ respectively) and all of the five fungi (0.78–25 µg ml⁻¹). Compounds **1c** and **1d** (tellurim derivative) possess a furan ring, which itself is known as bioactive moiety⁶ even then compound **1c** was found to be most active amongst all the compounds. It may be attributed that not only furan ring but also the presence of selenium is also responsible for high antimicrobial activity of the compounds.

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